

Calculations by Hand And Comprehension: A Case Study

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Abstract

The debate over impacts of introducing computers and calculators to classrooms lasts half a century now. While there is a strong case for introducing computing technology to education, the utility of preserving a meaningful component of work done by hand is less studied. In this contribution we report on changes applied to an introductory course on numerical methods, namely reintroduction of calculations done by hand, and their impact on student comprehension and their attitudes.

Introduction

The advent of calculators and computers has brought fundamental changes to education at all levels and raised some crucial questions. Computing skills became less important, which is in particular true about engineering. In the past decades, engineering practice shifted from calculations to the use of software packages. Engineers of the future will be informed users of mathematics; they will need to be able to formulate problems in the mathematical language, and interpret and validate the output of software solvers. Correspondingly, the focus of engineering education in mathematics shifted from procedural knowledge (derivation, integration) to conceptual knowledge.

Much work has been done on what we should teach future engineers, see SEFI (2013) and e.g. Pepin et al (2021) for overview. Students should gain certain mathematical competencies, see Niss (2003), but teaching students to "think mathematically" remains a significant challenge. This has traditionally been difficult, but there are two new factors connected with the current ubiquity of computing and information technology, namely, the reduction of memorization components and work done by hand in schools.

While these trends represent a natural reaction to changes in our civilization, excessive removal of memorization and hand work is detrimental to learning. Results from cognitive science, see e.g. Gilhooly (2004), show that knowledge stored in working memory is crucial for reasoning. In particular, Price et al (2013) address the effect of long-term memory learning on mathematical ability. This knowledge should be well structured. The internalization of knowledge can be helped by work done by hand. For instance, there is mounting evidence that making class notes and preparing study text by hand-writing, in particular using the connected cursive writing, is more beneficial compared to typing the same text, see e.g. Ose Askvik et al (2020). The underlying cognitive mechanism potentially applies also to mathematics.

There is numerous anecdotal evidence pointing to a relationship between significant practice in hand calculations and understanding of mathematics. For instance, there is a common impression (but it is hard to find supporting evidence) that insufficient experience with calculations by hand (in particular working with fractions) can be detrimental to the better appreciation of rules and of the importance of going by them, which later causes difficulties when manipulating abstract objects. It is conceivable that mental and hand calculations may stimulate the brain to develop certain capabilities that later support understanding of advanced mathematical concepts.

Some aspects of this problem have been well studied, for instance the impact of calculator use in classrooms in elementary and middle education. There seems to be a consensus that elementary operations should be mastered by hand before moving to calculators, but the utility of preserving hand calculations in later years and high school is less investigated. For an overview see e.g. Ellington (2003). Another aspect that deserves more study is the impact of pre-college work done by hand on mathematics performance at university. The studies that the author found (Wilson & Naiman (2004), Mogary & Faleye (2012)) suggest that there is a reason for concern, but typically they are small and specific. A more recent meta-analysis Mao et al (2017) does include delayed use of handheld devices until operations were mastered as one of the factors. It did not confirm a negative influence of insufficient work by hand, but this question was not the focus of the study.

If there is little data about the relationship between college performance and pre-college work by hand, there seems even less addressing the impact of work done by hand at university level. This contribution does not bring a definite answer either. It reports on a specific situation that shows that the questions we raised here may be important and deserving a further study.

The Beginning - A Computer-rich Course

In 2014, the author had the opportunity to design a new introductory course on differential equations and numerical methods. Initially it was to be a course offered to an honors program with a small enrolment (up to ten) of highly skilled and motivated students, and with a generous class time donation. A mixed-model was adopted, where students would practice solving ODEs analytically by hand and explore numerical methods using a user-friendly software in computer labs. The exam included a question asking students to explain the workings of a specific numerical method.

The course ran for about three years in this form with considerable success, and it was decided that it would be given to students of the majority of programs offered by the faculty, bringing the enrolment to about 300. Also, the number of weekly classes was lowered by one third by the administration. This brought significant challenges. In particular, surprisingly many students were not comfortable enough with classical computation technology (desktops, operating systems), and helping them took away a significant part of the already decrease computer time.

While technically the course worked, the compromises and generally weaker background and lower motivation of students compared to the special course resulted in lowered learning outcomes. The worst impact was seen in the numerical part of the exam: The majority of students failed to answer the “explain how it works” question. And not only did they fail it, about half of them did not even attempt to answer it.

The End - A Paper-and-pen Course

In 2019 we decided to prepare a new version of the course where students would familiarize themselves with numerical methods by applying them by hand once, before passing to (significantly reduced) computer experimentation. We started to teach this way in the spring of 2020, which was the right time, because when the first covid lockdown came, we were not hit as hard as we would be with the previous (more computer dependent) version of the course.

Running the course in this way in 2020 and 2021 we observed improved results and gained valuable experience. In particular, we found that many students found participation in discussion about numerical experiments sufficient and gave up on running them themselves while attending online sessions from home, without observable ill effects. Moreover, the overhead related to running the computer part of classes became out of proportion to its utility. We therefore decided to drop the active student computer component altogether.

In 2022 we therefore transitioned to a new format. All numerical work done by students in practical classes is done by hand (and perhaps calculators), to which end we prepared a database of computation-friendly problems that can be solved just using small integers or (at worst) simple fractions. Moreover, at the exam, points for a practical numerical problem (also solved by hand) are awarded mostly for applying the right method in the right way, for interpretation of results etc., so numerical errors do not really influence grades when/if they happen.

There is some computer experimentation preserved in practical classes, but it is ran by the instructor with student input. For motivated students we prepared annotated worksheets that they can run at their convenience.

While losing the practical computer component of the course has not been an easy choice, it made the practical classes more efficient, giving students more time to learn. As the results below show, this computer-less version of the course has comparable results to the mixed model from years 2020 and 2021, and students' comments are also very complimentary. Moreover, it simplified organization of the course.

The Outcome

When we decided to look for ways to improve student performance in the numerical segment of the exam, we decided to collect data. Going back to 2018, we recorded student performance on the question asking students to explain a specific numerical method. We

ranked the answers as complete, partial, and fails. Moreover, we recorded the attempt rate as an indication of self-confidence of students.

It should be noted that the results are comparable, as the form and difficulty of this question did not change over time, and even in the covid years the exams were taken on-site, under exactly the same conditions as before or after (the lockdowns affected only weeks of instruction).

In the following table we show the results. The number of exams taken by students is absolute, while the numbers in remaining columns are percentages taken against this number of exams. It should be noted that the actual enrolment in the course is typically 15 to 20 percent higher, but not all students make it to exams.

year	exams	attempt	correct	fail
2018	210	53.8	26.2	58.1
2019	245	55.9	25.3	56.3
2020	270	73.0	28.9	46.7
2021	317	94.0	48.9	17.4
2022	280	95.3	46.1	24.6
2023	272	96.3	49.6	22.4
2024	325	95.4	47.1	21.3

Table 1: Course results

The first percentage shows how many students did attempt the theoretical question. The introduction of hand-solved problems makes a clear impact in 2020. The gradual improvement makes sense, as in 2020 we were learning how to teach the new format properly and also adjusting to online teaching.

The second percentage number shows how many answers were satisfactory. Note that this number is also with respect to exams, not against the number of attempts. Since these two percentage numbers (attempts, success) are computed against the same base, they are directly comparable and show that consistently about half of the students who attempt this question succeed.

The last number shows failures. This number thus includes students who did not attempt this question and those who attempted but their answers were not even partially correct. The complement of the last two numbers to 100% shows answers that managed to capture the substance of the required method, but some important aspects were wrong or missing.

Since 2021 the results seems fairly consistent.

The author also observed a gradual change in student behavior. Many students come to university with the habit of pulling out their calculators at the first sign of trouble, and instead of trying to reason out the ideas behind a problem to be solved, they start punching in data and combine them in various ways, hoping to get enlightened. The new form of the course lead to a visible decrease of this behavior. The majority of students learn fairly soon during the course that they need not worry about calculations and it is better to focus

on “how”. In particular, there has been a significantly decreased use of calculators during final exams. However, since we did not quantify it before, we cannot support this impression by hard data.

Conclusion, Discussion

When interpreting statistical results, we have to consider various influences. When we observed a problem in the course, we naturally also tried to improve our instruction, making students more aware of what is expected of them. Thus it is not clear what part of the impressive improvements is due to students doing hand calculations. However, while changes in instruction were incremental, we see discrete changes in learning outcomes corresponding to introduction of problems solved by hand. Thus it is arguable that it contributed significantly to the reported results.

They seem to confirm observations made by other authors: When students use technology to solve problems, they tend to focus on the process of inputting data and reading answers, without worrying too much about what is happening in between. Related experience with project-based learning suggests that when students use some tools when solving an applied problem, they do not sufficiently focus on them to internalize them. Calculations done by hand channel student attention to the underlying ideas. The author feels that giving students experience with both calculations by hand and experimenting with software should provide the best result. Unfortunately, reduction in class time prevented having these two as meaningful components in the course.

Thus it is arguable that even in the computer age, calculations done by humans still have their place at universities. However, they should not be an end to itself and an empty drill. Rather, they should be used judiciously to help in development of mathematical competencies. When we decide to include problems worked on paper in our course, we should try to reduce student anxiety about making mistakes. Computation-friendly problems and a grading policy lenient toward numerical errors help to alleviate these concerns.

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